

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.289 Max: 62.313	1479 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropogenic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 2205-2207 Photo Model: Yes No #: 353

DEFINITION: *fragmented imbrex used as burial container*

Covered by SU: 1478 Fills SU: 1483 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL MATRIX														
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles f <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)														
			clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive														
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

grave 45

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):*
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1478	Covers: 1482
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by: 1480, 1481	Fills: 1483

OBSERVATIONS: *dry, sunny conditions, good visibility, SU had been topped in an*

was later removed from site

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *last central in area B 2011*

Shape: *semicircular to long rectangular as imbrices usually tend to be*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): *No slope*

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

Sketch of imbrax

INTERPRETATION

Partially fragmented imbrax which has been used as burial container for an infant burial.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CHM	on	2.8.2011
Revised by	CHM	on	2.8.2011
PDFd by	ECR	on	3.8.2011
Entered by		on	